

THE ROLE OF "GREEN COVER" IN RESTORING ECOSYSTEM BALANCE

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Abstract. *The given article presents information on the significance of water in restoring ecosystem balance and the planting of saxaul seeds in the sand desert lands of the Uchkuduk Forestry District using small aviation (Motodeltaplan) between 2022-2024. Specifically, it discusses how the initially planted saxaul forests are now producing seeds, dispersing them to the surrounding area, and contributing to the natural restoration and stabilization of the phytocenosis. Additionally, it is forecasted that the forestry reclamation works will yield results over time.*

Keywords: *Uchkuduk Forestry District, 115 km to 125 km, flora and fauna representatives.*

It is important to suggest that at present time the process of climate change and the tightening of ecological balance are being observed worldwide. These trends can also be tracked through media and online data. In some areas, flooding is occurring, while in others, the process of water scarcity is becoming more noticeable. Water scarcity is turning into an urgent issue, and in this context, it is important to use water efficiently, apply modern water-saving technologies, and carry out scientifically grounded irrigation practices to conserve water.

In the article "A Drop of Water" by "New Uzbekistan" correspondent Avazbek Khudoykulov, the following information is presented:

The United Nations World Desertification and Drought Organization, in its statement last year, noted that by 2050, drought could affect more than two-thirds of the world's population. This is a significant figure, and naturally, it is concerning for our country's climate, especially regarding the stability of water supply. This concern is confirmed by the fact that over the past 15 years, the amount of precipitation in our country has decreased by 25%.

According to research by the World Resources Institute and the Economist Intelligence Unit from the UK, by 2040, among the 33 countries likely to experience the highest levels of water scarcity, Central Asian countries, particularly Uzbekistan, are included [<https://yuz.uz/news/bir-tomchi-suv>]. At the same time, the author provides the following information while analyzing global drip irrigation practices:

As a result, a global market for drip irrigation technologies worth \$9.3 billion has formed. Researcher Komiljon Koziev states, "According to experts from the University of Rhode Island in the USA, by 2028, this market will reach \$23.3 billion, nearly 2.5 times the current figure."

This emphasizes the growing global recognition of the importance of efficient water management and the increasing demand for technologies that optimize water usage, such as drip irrigation systems, which are essential for ensuring sustainable agricultural practices.

According to Fortune Business Insight, the market for drip irrigation technologies in Asia is valued at 4.3 billion dollars. This market is projected to grow at an average annual rate of 9.3%,

and by 2026, it is expected to account for 40% of the global market [<https://yuz.uz/news/bir-tomchi-suv>].

In line with the available opportunities, the cultivation of young seedlings through drip irrigation in fallow lands is also expected to yield positive results.

Based on our long-term research and the results obtained during scientific experiments, we intend to approach the mitigation of this ecological situation in the following way.

Indeed, in our country, the reduction of water resources is being observed due to changes in precipitation levels, leading to various water-related issues across different regions.

From a forestry perspective, it is most effective to utilize plant species based on their biological and ecological characteristics in different regions. This involves using plants that thrive in water-scarce, arid lands and sandy desert areas. In our research conducted in the desert sands of the Uchkuduk Forestry District, we have achieved the following results.

The "New Uzbekistan" development strategy for 2022-2026 has set the goal to create 500,000 hectares of green areas in the dried bed of the Aral Sea, and by the end of 2026, the total area of green spaces will reach 2.5 million hectares, which constitutes 78% of the region. Accordingly, several desert plants, especially saxaul will be widely used for creating green cover in these desert areas. In this regard, it is considered appropriate to plant saxaul seeds using small aviation (Motodeltaplan) to ensure high-quality seed planting.

In our practical research, forest reclamation work was carried out in the sandy desert areas of Uchkuduk Forestry, Navoi region, where green cover was established using small aviation (ultralight aircraft). In studying the current condition and evaluating the growth and development processes of desert plants grown from seeds, significant results were achieved.

Between 2022-2024, the height of the saxaul trees planted for the purpose of creating green cover ranged from 0.20 m to 1.7 meters. These saxaul plants, which were planted in the earlier years, have now produced seeds and are dispersing them around, contributing to the restoration of the natural phytocenosis of the area.

Fig 1. View of the saxaul plantation grown with the help of ultralight aircraft.

As a result of this afforestation, the ecosystem in the sandy desert of Uchkuduk Forestry region, Navoi is being restored, creating favorable conditions for the increase of plant cover.

Between the 115 km and 125 km range in the sandy areas, saxaul seeds were sown, with seedling growth rates varying from 3% to 25% (relative to the area) in areas with low salinity. In some areas, the seedlings are growing in isolated patches.

In 2024, along both sides of the sandy desert area, saxaul seeds were sown using ultralight aircraft (Motodeltaplan) with the aim of stabilizing the sand and creating green cover. The growth

rates of the seeds ranged from 3% to 25%, depending on the region, with some areas, such as between 118 km, showing up to 25% growth, as mentioned earlier. In other regions, however, growth was observed in 4-5 size (an area unit, approximately 0.01 hectares) locations only, on average per hectare. This growth rate is considered an effective result in this desert ecosystem, as biological productivity will begin after 4-5 years. In other words, based on the natural laws of nature, the increase in phytocenosis will help expand the green cover areas.

Fig.2 1-2 year-old saxaul seedlings grown with the help of ultralight aircraft.

Thus, in the initial years (between 5-7 years), the planting works will be followed by the natural laws and physical principles, leading to increased fertility in the soil. As a result, phytocenosis mass and composition will enrich over time.

In the following years, this will result in beneficial effects in the area. Ecological balance will stabilize, and the moisture content of the soil will increase, preventing the increase of sand and dust. This process follows the biological laws of nature and takes time.

By summarising it should be suggested that while natural restoration yields results, the sandy desert areas in Navoi region will require no further investment over the years. This will contribute to the increase in biodiversity of flora and fauna in the region, resulting in improved green energy efficiency.

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